

EXPERIMENTAL VERIFICATION OF SPRINGBACK PHENOMENON ANALYSIS BY FBG SENSORS AND IMAGE PROCESSING METHODS IN A C/PPS COMPOSITE

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1 Introduction

This paper presents measurements of the springback angle of a C/PPS composite plate with single curvature with the use of optical FBG sensors. Springback is an angular change caused by residual stresses set in the composite during curing in a closed form. The analytical model was written in Matlab code and then transformed into Java, where software with a GUI was developed. The predicted springback angle was verified using data from the manufacturer and also by measurements performed in our lab.

2 Springback Phenomenon

2.1 Analytical Description

Residual stresses that are set in the fiber-reinforced composites while a laminate is being cured in closed form lead to dimensional changes of composites after they are extracted from the form and cooled down. One of these dimensional changes is the so-called springback of angle sections. Other dimensional changes include warpage of flat sections and the displacement of single layers of composite. The manufacturing technology is shown in Fig. 1, and the springback effect on a U-shape composite part is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1. Manufacturing technology.

Fig. 2. Distortion of molded U-section.

Temperature change of dimensions is related to many parameters, e.g. the angle of the composite part, the thickness of the laminate, lay-up, flange length, and also tool material, tool surface or cure cycle [1, 2]. Published papers usually describe the effect of springback on the behavior of a composite L (or U) section extracted from a form that has been cooled down to room temperature; see Fig. 1. The analytical model that covers temperature change, chemical shrinkage during curing and moisture change was used to describe the change of the angle section. It is shown in the next equation,

$$\Delta\gamma = \Delta\gamma_t + \Delta\gamma_{h\Box} + \Delta\gamma_c = \gamma \frac{(\alpha_x - \alpha_z)\Delta T}{1 + \alpha_z \Delta T} + \gamma \frac{(\beta_x - \beta_z)\Delta c}{1 + \beta_z} + \gamma \frac{(\phi_x - \phi_z)}{1 + \phi_z} \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta\gamma_t$ is the temperature part of angle change, $\Delta\gamma_h$ is the change in angle due to a hygroscopic effect and $\Delta\gamma_c$ is the change in angle due to a shrinkage effect during the cure cycle [1]. The temperature term of Eq.(1) can be re-written into the equation describing the springback as a relative change in the section angle [3]

$$SB = \Delta\gamma/\gamma_T = = \frac{(\alpha_y - \alpha_z)\Delta T}{1 + \alpha_z \Delta T} = \frac{\varepsilon_y^T - \varepsilon_z^T}{1 + \varepsilon_z^T} \quad (2)$$

For the unsymmetrical lay-up, an additional term must be included in Eq.(3)

$$SB = R\kappa_y^T + \frac{\varepsilon_y^T - \varepsilon_z^T}{1 + \varepsilon_z^T} \quad (3)$$

where κ_y^T is the change in curvature and R is the radius affecting the straight part of the plate. The change in curvature is given by:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_x^{0,T} \\ \varepsilon_y^{0,T} \\ \gamma_{xy}^{0,T} \\ \kappa_x^T \\ \kappa_y^T \\ \kappa_{xy}^T \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{16} & b_{11} & b_{12} & b_{16} \\ a_{12} & a_{22} & a_{26} & b_{12} & b_{22} & b_{26} \\ a_{16} & a_{26} & a_{66} & b_{16} & b_{26} & b_{66} \\ b_{11} & b_{12} & b_{16} & d_{11} & d_{12} & d_{16} \\ b_{12} & b_{22} & b_{26} & d_{21} & d_{22} & d_{26} \\ b_{16} & b_{26} & b_{66} & d_{16} & d_{26} & d_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} N_x^T \\ N_y^T \\ N_{xy}^T \\ M_x^T \\ M_y^T \\ M_{xy}^T \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

When the cylindrical shell of diameter $D=2R_y$ is analyzed, this springback effect must be included in the thermal force-strain relationship of laminated plates. This is accomplished by making the following replacement in Eq.(4).

$$\kappa_y^T \Rightarrow \kappa_y^T + \frac{1}{R_y} (\varepsilon_y^T - \varepsilon_z^T) \quad (5)$$

The hygroscopic and shrinkage terms of Eq.(1) can be modified in a similar way. The calculation of ε_z^T is described in detail in [3]. In our case, we investigated a C/PPS springback composite, with the fiber volume fraction $V_f = 49\%$ and $[(0,90)/(\pm 45)]_4/(0,90)_s$ lay-up.

The model, which was implemented into Java, also gives the user the option of choosing the micromechanics of straight fibers, undulated fibers (fabrics with a plain, twill and satin weave – see Fig. 3 for details) and direct input of the S matrix and thermal expansion, moisture absorption and matrix shrinkage vectors.

In each type of weave, an area can be found which is regularly repeated. After an analysis of this area, we obtain three types of elements which characterize the weave. Element I has both fibers undulated (typical for a plain weave), element II has both fibers

straight, and element III has at least one fiber curved. It can be shown that a twill and satin weave can be composed from elements I and II [6]. Element I is the basic type, because the other types are special cases of element I. To calculate the properties of element I, we have to accept some presumptions

- the whole thickness of the element is the sum of the thickness of the fabric and the thickness of the matrix
- the weave of the fabric is tight
- the curvature of the fibers is regular (sinusoidal) and the fibers are prismatic
- the fibers in the cross-section are distributed equally
- the matrix and fibers are linearly elastic, the matrix is isotropic, and the fibers are transversally isotropic
- the temperature is the same throughout the volume, no residual stresses exist, and there are no other components and defects in the composite, apart from the fiber and the matrix

The user can also input a different volumetric fiber content for each layer (which can simulate the gradient of the volumetric fiber fraction in the radius) and can compose every lay-up from a different matrix and fiber (also with a user-defined material). This gives the option of composing inter-laminar and intra-laminar hybrid composites. The flowchart of the software is shown can be seen in Fig. 4. The print screen of the GUI is shown in Fig. 5.

Fig.3. Types of weaves (plain, twill and satin).

Fig.4. Flowchart of the software.

Fig.5. GUI of the software

3 Experiment

3.1 FBG sensors

A Fiber Bragg Grating (FBG) sensor is an intrinsic spectrometric type of sensor. FBG sensors have been developed intensively since their invention in the early 1990s. They are based on a periodic variation in the refractive index of the fiber core, which reflects particular wavelengths of light and transmits all the rest.

Two types of grating period are mainly used for the purposes of FBG sensing:

- *Uniform*: the grating period is constant along the FBG sensing area. The reflected peak is narrow.
- *Chirped*: the grating period is gradually distributed along the optical fiber. The reflected spectrum is wider than the spectrum from uniform FBG. Moreover, the wavelength of the reflected light corresponds to the position in the grating/sensor section of the fiber.

A typical measurement configuration for an FBG sensor is pictured in Fig.6 (see [4] for details).

Fig.6. Experimental configuration for measurement with FBG sensor [4].

The broadband light spectrum from an optic source is guided by the optic fiber into the FBG sensor. Part of the light is reflected by the grating in the form of a narrow Gaussian peak, and the rest is transmitted. For sensing purposes, the reflected peak is commonly measured using a spectrometer.

The working principle of an FBG sensor is based on the sensitivity of the grating period and the refractive index to changes in strain and temperature. Each Bragg grating is characterized by the so-called Bragg wavelength λ_B , which is defined as follows:

$$\lambda_B = 2n\Lambda \quad (6)$$

where n is refractive core index and Λ is grating pitch. The central (Bragg) wavelength shifts according to the deformation of the grating. Elongation causes a positive shift, while shortening causes a negative shift. The wavelength shift response to strain ϵ and temperature change ΔT is expressed by the equation:

$$\frac{\Delta\lambda_B}{\lambda_B} = P\varepsilon + [P(\alpha_S - \alpha_F) + \xi] \quad (7)$$

where P is the strain-optic coefficient, α_S is the coefficient of thermal expansion of the specimen, α_F is the coefficient of thermal expansion of the fiber, and ξ is the thermo-optic coefficient.

A linear response of the FBG sensor to strain and temperature was observed. Typical values for the sensitivity of the FBG sensor to a change in strain and temperature were measured for two common fiber coating materials: *Polyacrylate* (fiber diameter 125 μm , coating diameter 250 μm) and *ORMOCER*[®] (fiber diameter 125 μm , coating diameter 195 μm). In our case, an *ORMOCER*[®] type of sensor was used. It has sensitivity to temperature 7,5 pm/K and sensitivity to strain 0,66 pm.

Two temperature compensation methods are commonly used for FBG sensors. The first method is based on strain measurement on two identical specimens, both with installed FBG sensors. The first specimen is loaded in a testing machine, while the second specimen is unloaded (influenced only by changes in the ambient temperature). Pure strain readings are obtained by subtracting the temperature readings (unloaded specimen) from the strain/temperature readings (loaded specimen).

The second compensation method is based on calibrating the strain response to the temperature change. The FBG sensor is temperature-calibrated after installation on the surface of the specimen (or after integration into the structure). The specimen with the FBG sensor is then placed in a laboratory furnace, and the temperature is gradually increased. The calibration curve is evaluated from the free strain of the specimen. The temperature is measured during the experiment, and compensation is made off-line, by calculation [4].

3.2 Description of the experiment

The initial angle of the specimen was measured at room temperature, i.e. 20°C (the measurement is to be made while the specimen is being heated). The angle was measured using a ScanControl 2800-25 laser profilometer. The specimen was measured in three places, and the average value was calculated. The measurement equipment is shown in Fig.7.

Fig.7. Measurement of the angle using ScanControl. Fig.8 shows the evaluation of the data and the calculation of the initial angle. The average value of the initial angle was **89,517°** (computed from the slopes of the lines, see Fig. 8). The specimen was heated to 175°C, and then cooled to room temperature and measured again. The initial angle after the second measurement was **89,381°**. This indicates an error of 0,152%, which is within the area of sensitivity and accuracy of the measurement method. It is therefore not necessary to measure the initial angle after each heating and cooling cycle.

Fig.8. Evaluation of the measured angle with ScanControl.

A C/PPS composite plate with single curvature was incised on the edges. Metal tubes were bonded to these incisions. An ORMOCER® FBG sensor was bonded inside these tubes (see Fig. 9 for details). The specimen was put into an oven with digitally controlled heating and heated to 175°C (the relationship between oven temperature and time is shown in Fig. 10). A second FBG sensor has to be put into the oven for temperature compensation. The value for the elongation of the FBG sensor was obtained in each temperature step. This is related to the change in the angle of the specimen.

Fig.9. Specimen with FBG sensor, prepared for experiment.

Fig.10. Relationship between oven temperature and time.

The camera was placed in front of the oven and a contrasting background was placed behind the

specimen in the oven (see Fig. 11 for details). In defined steps, the door of the oven was opened and photos were taken of the specimen. The springback angle was evaluated in parallel from the figures using image processing software, with the data obtained from the FBG sensor.

Fig.11. Measurement arrangement.

3.3 Evaluation of the measured data

During the test heating, which was not evaluated, the FBG sensor slipped out from the bonded layer inside the metal tube due to thermal expansion of the tube. After cooling down, the fiber was no longer pre-stressed, so we could not make any more measurements with it. However, the specimen was repaired and prepared for the next measurement. The measured data shows the temperature (or the time) when it slipped out. Fig. 12 is the reference photo with the scale that was used during image processing.

Fig.12. Reference photo with the scale for image processing.

Data from the FBG sensor was evaluated in Matlab script and is shown in Fig. 13. Average values for loaded and compensation fiber and the difference between them are shown in Fig. 14.

Fig.13. Relationship between the strain of FBG and time.

Fig.14. Average values of the strain of FBG, and their difference.

The two figures show that the FBG sensor measured just till 1500 s (which corresponds to a temperature of 120°C). The strain on the vertical axis was recalculated to the absolute elongation (see Fig. 15). The time from the horizontal axis was recalculated to the corresponding temperatures: 40°C, 80°C and 120°C.

Fig.15. Relationship between absolute elongation and time.

4 Results

The data measured with the FBG sensor was compared with the data from the camera and the predicted analytical solution, see Fig. 16. The change in temperature on the horizontal axis is taken to the reference temperature of 20°C at which the initial angle was measured. A comparison of the data from the FBG sensor and from the camera is relevant until 120°C because the sensor slipped out at this point: the springback for temperatures above 120°C was measured just by the camera. Pictures from the camera were evaluated in GraphReader software in a similar way as the initial angle measured with the ScanControl profilometer (see Fig. 8 – angle computation from the slopes of the lines).

Fig.16. Comparison of analytical and experimental results.

A comparison of the experimental results from the FBG sensor and from image processing shows the same trend as the analytical prediction. The differences may be due to the different recrystallization shrinkage value (the specimen is heated and some crystals may still have been grown from the previous process).

The measurement with FBG sensors and image correlation was compared with the earlier measurement made to 95°C (below the recrystallization effect) [5]. The measuring equipment that was used earlier was a PT100 temperature sensor, a CRZ Platinum thin film element, a FLUKE 574 contactless infrared thermometer, a ScanControl LLT 2800-25 laser profilometer and CHRcodile M4 optical distance measurement (see Fig. 17 and 18). A comparison of all measurements with the analytical prediction is shown in Fig. 19.

Fig.17. Experimental devices.

Fig.18. Measurement with ScanControl.

Fig.19. Comparison of analytical and experimental results from all measurements

5 Conclusions

A measurement of the springback angle of a thermoplastic composite plate with single curvature, including the recrystallization effect, was made in our lab. The springback angle was measured with FBG optical sensors in parallel with image processing. This measurement was compared with a previous measurement, which did not include the recrystallization effect (the specimen was heated just to 95°C). The earlier measurement and the new measurement were compared with the Springback software analytical solution. Good agreement was achieved.

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